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Report

Successful treatment of narcolepsy with prednisolone

Abstract

Narcolepsy is a chronic neurological disorder with symptoms that include excessive daytime sleepiness and cataplexy. While the traditional understanding of narcolepsy has been centered on genetic and autoimmune causes, recent studies have begun to explore connections with brain injury and mitochondrial diseases (mitochondriopathies). This paper reports a case of successful treatment of severe narcolepsy-like symptoms with prednisolone, a corticosteroid. This finding may lead to more targeted and personalized therapeutic approaches for individuals suffering from narcolepsy or narcolepsy-like symptoms linked to brain injury or mitochondrial dysfunction.

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Introduction

Narcolepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by excessive daytime sleepiness, cataplexy, sleep paralysis, and hypnagogic hallucinations. The etiology of this complex disorder remains a topic of intense study. Recently, there has been an increased interest in exploring the relationships between narcolepsy, brain injury, and mitochondrial diseases, known as mitochondrialopathies.^{1,2,14,15,16} This paper reports about a patient whose narcolepsy-like symptoms vanish almost entirely under treatment with corticosteroids.

Narcolepsy and brain injury

Brain injury can lead to a multitude of neurological symptoms, and in some instances, has been linked to narcolepsy-like symptoms. It has been postulated that trauma to the brain can damage the hypothalamic region where hypocretin (also known as orexin) neurons are located. Since hypocretin is essential for maintaining wakefulness, a decrease in its production can lead to the well known symptoms of narcolepsy. The underlying pathophysiology connecting brain injury to narcolepsy is complex. Several studies have indicated that traumatic brain injury (TBI) might lead to autoimmune responses against the hypocretin neurons. These responses might cause the reduction or elimination of hypocretin, resulting in narcolepsy symptoms.^{5,9,10,13,}

Mitochondriopathies and narcolepsy-like seizures

Mitochondriopathies refer to a group of disorders caused by dysfunction in the mitochondria, the energy-producing structures within cells. These disorders often affect tissues with high energy requirements, including the the endocrine system and the brain. Mitochondriopathies can lead to a range of neurological symptoms, and in some cases, narcolepsy-like seizures have been reported.

The pathogenesis of narcolepsy-like seizures in mitochondrialopathies is not entirely understood. However, it is believed to involve cellular dysfunction and neuronal degeneration. Mitochondrial dysfunction may lead to an imbalance in the cellular energy supply, resulting in neural instability. This instability could, in turn, lead to narcolepsy-like seizures.^{17,18}

Treatment and Management

The treatment of narcolepsy and narcolepsy-like seizures in the context of brain injury and mitochondrialopathies requires a multidisciplinary approach. This might include pharmacological interventions, such as the use of modafinil to promote wakefulness or sodium oxybate to control cataplexy. In cases of mitochondrial dysfunction, supplementation with coenzyme Q10 and other mitochondrial nutrients are often mentioned as beneficial without solid proof. We report a treatment with prednisolone.

Narcolepsy and narcolepsy-like seizures present a significant challenge to healthcare providers. The connections between these conditions and brain injury or mitochondrialopathies provide new insights into the pathogenesis and potential treatment strategies. However, much remains to be understood about these complex interactions, and further research is needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms and develop more targeted therapies. Further understanding of these connections will be instrumental in providing personalized care to individuals with narcolepsy or narcolepsy-like symptoms arising from brain injury or mitochondrial dysfunction, and can pave the way for the development of novel therapeutic strategies tailored to individual etiologies.¹⁻¹⁸

Case

In 2018, a 43-year-old man was diagnosed with narcolepsy accompanied by cataplexy, set against the background of a PDH mitochondrial cytopathy. Over time, he manifested a progressive trend of excessive daytime sleep attacks and cataplexy, with a particular accentuation in the postprandial period. Various stimulating medications were prescribed to address these symptoms, though none proved efficacious. Subsequent to the diagnosis of a rather serious skin condition, a corollary of his mitochondrialopathy, he was administered a daily dose of 45 mg of prednisolone for one week. Remarkably, just one day after the initiation of corticoid treatment, his narcoleptic symptoms receded almost entirely. Upon the cessation of steroid treatment following one week - coinciding with a marked improvement in his skin condition - his narcolepsy reemerged instantaneously, in a time frame corresponding with the half-life of prednisolone. Resuming prednisolone therapy at a reduced daily dose of 30 mg, the patient's narcoleptic symptoms persisted, albeit at a diminished intensity. However, when the dosage was escalated to > 40 mg per day, his narcolepsy

abated once more. The therapeutic effect proved so profound that the patient assented to endure the potential adverse consequences of prolonged steroid treatment. Now, after an 18-month regimen of prednisolone, he continues to experience an 80% improvement in his narcoleptic symptoms compared to the pre-corticoid steroid treatment baseline.

Conclusion

Our discovery underscores the necessity for more targeted and personalized therapeutic strategies for individuals afflicted with narcolepsy or narcolepsy-like symptoms, particularly those associated with brain injury or mitochondrial dysfunction.

Conflicts of interest

None

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